

Effects of short-term ingestion of different sitosterol esters on plasma lipids, faecal steroids, fats and proteins in rats

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Abstract : Sterol and sterol esters are naturally occurring antioxidants available mainly from vegetable oils. The modification in compositions of these natural antioxidants leads to the production of nutraceuticals. The purpose of the present study was to compare the effects of different n-3 fatty acid rich sitosterol esters on plasma lipid lowering, faecal fat and steroid excretion. The difference in efficacy between the two esters (EPA-DHA and ALA rich sitosterol ester) in rats fed with a high cholesterol diet was also observed. Thirty six rats were taken for the study and were divided into 6 groups : control group, hypercholesterolemic group, EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester treated and ALA rich sitosterol ester treated group with two different doses (0.25 g/kg body wt/day, 0.5 g/kg body wt/day). The sterol esters were gavaged to the rats daily for 4 weeks. The plasma total cholesterol, non-HDL cholesterol and triglyceride levels were elevated in hypercholesterolemic group but was significantly lowered by both the sterol esters. The high dose of EPA-DHA rich sterol ester showed the best result. Faecal cholesterol and total lipid excretion increased in the treated groups than the hypercholesterolemic one. Faecal protein excretion decreased in the treated groups in comparison to the hypercholesterolemic one which revealed that protein was utilized better in the bodies in presence of sterol esters. In conclusion EPA-DHA rich sterol ester produced better nutraceutical properties in comparison to ALA rich sterol ester.

Abbreviations : EPA – Eicosa-penta-enoic acid (C_{20:5}); DHA – Docosa-hexanoic acid (C_{22:6}); ALnA – Alpha linolenic acid (C_{18:3}).

Keywords : Sitosterol esters, faecal steroids, plasma lipids, lipid excretion, protein excretion.

Introduction

Sterol and sterol esters are natural component of vegetable oils, present in various forms and various amounts. These phytosterols are nonnutritive compounds (or phytochemicals) with the same basic functions in plants as cholesterol in animals; i.e. they regulate the membrane fluidity of plant cells and other physiological functions associated with plant biology. Many studies have demonstrated the ability of phytosterol to reduce blood cholesterol levels in hyper- and normocholesterolemic subjects^{1,2}. Investigators reported that phytosterol intake of 2–3 g/d reduce low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol levels by about 10% in human subjects³. Other beneficial effects from phytosterols include anti-inflammatory⁴ and antipyretics. It has been demonstrated that free phytosterol can decrease blood cholesterol concentrations by mainly suppressing cholesterol absorption from the intestinal lu-

men with inhibition of micelle formation between cholesterol and bile acids and/or lipids⁵⁻⁷. Similarly sterol esters also possess some nutritive functions in human physiology.

There is evidence to suggest that n-3 fatty acids in the diet have protective effects against cardiovascular disease^{8,9}. It is significant that n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 PUFA) present in fish oil appear to be much effective in reducing hyperlipidemia. Schmidt *et al.* observed the effect of n-3 PUFA supplementation in men with moderate and severe hypertriglyceridemia and indicated that total cholesterol and triglycerides decreased significantly¹⁰.

However, it is difficult to ingest effective amounts of free sitosterols continuously as a food supplement because of its poor solubility in lipids⁸. In contrast, phytosterol esters, which is esterified with a fatty acid, dis-

solves well in lipids and is well accepted by body. Sitosterols if esterified with n-3 PUFAs like eicosa pentanoic acid (EPA), docosa-hexanoic acid (DHA) and alpha-linolenic acid (ALA) will probably increase the anti-hyperlipidemic effect due to the combined effect of sitosterols and n-3 fatty acids.

The present study was designed to compare the plasma lipid lowering, faecal fat and steroid excretion after a short-term ingestion of EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester and ALA rich sitosterol ester and to evaluate the difference in efficacy of these two esters in hypercholesterolemic rats.

Table 1. Experimental diet groups

Group	Name of group	Diet
1 (n = 6)	Control	Stock diet with groundnut oil
2 (n = 6)	Hypercholesterolemic control	Stock diet with groundnut and cholesterol (1% of dietary oil)
3 (n = 6)	Experimental Ia	Group 2 diet with EPA-DHA phytosterol ester as a therapeutic dose of 0.25 g/kg body wt/day
4 (n = 6)	Experimental Ib	Group 2 diet with EPA-DHA phytosterol ester as a therapeutic dose of 0.5 g/kg body wt/day
5 (n = 6)	Experimental IIa	Group 2 diet with ALA phytosterol ester as a therapeutic dose of 25 g/kg body wt/day
6 (n = 6)	Experimental IIb	Group 2 diet with ALA phytosterol ester as a therapeutic dose of 0.5 g/kg body wt/day

Results

Fatty acid composition of phytosterol esters :

The transesterification reaction was carried out in the packed bed reactor. In the first set of reaction fish oil was used as a source of EPA and DHA fatty acids and in the second set, linseed oil was used as a source of ALA fatty acid. Approximately 32% EPA and 22% DHA was present in fish oil and 54% of ALA in linseed oil. Analysis of fatty acid composition of sterol-esters by GC showed that almost all the fatty acids present in the different oils (in TAG form) were incorporated in the corresponding esters. Table 2 shows the fatty acid profile of the two sitosterol esters in packed bed bioreactor.

Gain in body weight :

The changes in the body weights of the male Wistar rats of the normal and experimental groups are shown in Table 3. There was a progressive increase in body weight of all groups.

Changes in the concentration of plasma lipids :

The plasma lipid profile of rats of different groups is shown in Table 4. The type of fat consumed altered the different lipid concentration in plasma. Rats fed with control Groundnut Oil had plasma total cholesterol of 54.37 mg/dL which was significantly increased to 246.83 mg/dL by feeding them with high cholesterol diet. Both the doses of sitosterol ester brought about a decrease in total cholesterol which was much more in case of EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester. The higher doses produced better hypocholesterolemic effect than the lower dose. Similar results were found in case of estimation of non-HDL cholesterol levels and triglyceride levels. Thus the sterol esters lowered the levels of non-HDL cholesterol and

Table 2. Fatty acid profiles of EPA-DHA rich and ALnA rich sterol esters used as nutraceutical

Fatty acid Sample	Fatty acid (% w/w)												
	C _{14:0}	C _{16:0}	C _{18:0}	C _{18:1}	C _{18:2}	C _{18:3}	C _{20:0}	C _{20:1}	C _{20:5}	C _{22:0}	C _{22:1}	C _{24:0}	C _{22:6}
Phytosterol- EPA-DHA ester	0.10 ± 0.00	2.44 ± 0.04	1.23 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.15	1.90 ± 0.27	3.05 ± 0.34	2.75 ± 0.64	5.12 ± 0.83	39.20 ± 1.10	5.65 ± 0.37	2.19 ± 0.08	3.84 ± 0.19	31.98 ± 1.63
Phytosterol- ALA ester	-	12.48 ± 0.60	1.89 ± 0.17	28.28 ± 1.09	12.83 ± 1.01	44.52 ± 1.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3. Body weight of normal and hypercholesterolemic groups

Body weight (g)	Control	Hypercholesterolemic	Ia	Ib	IIa	IIb
d 0	123.33 ± 1.22	120.00 ± 0.77	194.16 ± 0.07	128.33 ± 0.11	130.00 ± 0.13	147.50 ± 0.20
d 7	137.50 ± 2.30	122.50 ± 0.23	193.33 ± 0.11	127.50 ± 0.19	131.67 ± 0.06	147.67 ± 0.29
d 14	155.83 ± 2.45	128.22 ± 0.56	200.00 ± 1.22	129.17 ± 1.43	132.00 ± 0.16	148.99 ± 0.56
d 21	156.67 ± 0.98	137.92 ± 1.20	200.83 ± 0.66	131.67 ± 0.89	132.50 ± 0.07	154.99 ± 0.24
d 28	158.90 ± 0.09	139.90 ± 0.67	208.22 ± 0.88	132.67 ± 0.56	135.00 ± 0.99	156.78 ± 0.23

Table 4. Plasma lipid profile of normal and hypercholesterolemic groups

Parameters	Control	Hypercholesterolemic	Ia	Ib	IIa	IIb
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	54.37 ± 1.20 ^a	246.83 ± 11.32 ^b	87.07 ± 2.30 ^c	63.27 ± 2.45 ^d	96.76 ± 1.98 ^c	65.75 ± 0.40 ^d
HDL cholesterol	23.98 ± 1.22 ^a	12.23 ± 1.09 ^b	20.80 ± 0.98 ^c	39.19 ± 0.38 ^d	23.36 ± 0.44 ^a	34.23 ± 1.76 ^e
Non-HDL	20.39 ± 0.77 ^a	213.44 ± 3.40 ^b	54.21 ± 0.99 ^c	14.52 ± 0.78 ^d	58.66 ± 1.56 ^e	20.63 ± 0.56 ^a
Triglycerides	49.98 ± 0.57 ^a	105.79 ± 4.50 ^b	60.32 ± 0.59 ^c	47.82 ± 0.33 ^a	73.69 ± 1.89 ^d	54.47 ± 2.90 ^e

Values are mean ± S.E.M. (n = 6 rats). Values not sharing a common superscript within a row are statistically significant (p < 0.05).

triglyceride significantly (p < 0.05). The level of HDL cholesterol, which was known as good cholesterol, increased significantly (p < 0.05) by treating the rats with phytosterol esters. The increase in the HDL level was much more in case of the rats treated with EPA-DHA rich sterol ester.

Faecal lipid and protein excretion :

The amount of excretion of lipid and protein in the faeces is shown in Table 5. From the results it was clear that there was difference in excretion of lipids of the different dietary groups. However, the protein excretion markedly increased in case of hypercholesterolemia which was decreased by the treatment of the rats with sterol esters.

Faecal steroid excretion :

Fig. 1 shows the comparison between the excretion of cholesterol and sitosterol and cholesterol ester in the faeces of the different groups. The results depicted that the excretion of cholesterol enhanced markedly (p < 0.05) in all the drug treated groups in comparison with the hypercholesterolemic control group. On the other hand the excretion of sitosterol decreased in the drug treated group. The excretion of cholesterol was maximum and the excretion of sitosterol was least in the group treated with the higher dose of EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester.

Table 5. Changes in faecal lipid and protein excretion in normal and hypercholesterolemic groups

Groups	Lipid excretion	Protein excretion
Control	13.49 ± 0.22 ^a	11.61 ± 0.09 ^a
Hypercholesterolemic	16.76 ± 0.34 ^b	17.69 ± 0.07 ^b
Ia	14.73 ± 0.45 ^c	10.92 ± 0.11 ^a
Ib	16.05 ± 0.08 ^d	5.18 ± 0.34 ^c
IIa	11.67 ± 0.34 ^e	14.87 ± 0.87 ^d
IIb	15.94 ± 0.23 ^d	6.51 ± 0.55 ^e

Values are mean ± S.E.M. (n = 6 rats). Values not sharing a common superscript within a column are statistically significant (p < 0.05).

Fig. 1. Comparison between sitosterol and cholesterol excretion in the faeces.

Discussion

The present study was undertaken to examine the effect of EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester and ALA rich sitosterol ester on serum lipids, faecal lipids and steroid excretion in rats fed with hypercholesterolemic diet. In the recent study, we prepared the phytosterol esters by enzymatic transesterification of β -sitosterol and two types of oils, namely fish oil and linseed oil. EPA, DHA and ALA were incorporated in the ester in quiet appreciable amounts to produce two types of n-3 PUFA rich sitosterol esters. In our investigation, we have tried to validate the mechanism of action of n-3 PUFA rich sitosterol esters in producing a hypolipidemic effect on hypercholesterolemic subjects.

Compared to the control group in the hypercholesterolemic (HCD) group there was a sharp increase in the total cholesterol (TC), triglyceride (TG) and non-high density lipoprotein cholesterol (non-HDL-C) levels. When the HCD group was fed with the sitosterol esters, there was significant lowering ($p < 0.05$) in plasma TC concentration, TG and non-HDL-C levels. On the other hand there was significant increase in the excretion of the TC in the faeces with a decrease in the total sitosterol concentration in experimental group compared to the HCD group. The nutraceutical effect of the higher dose (50 mg/rat/day) in case of both the esters was more beneficial than the lower dose (25 mg/rat/day).

Administration as esters signifies that they must first be hydrolyzed by the pancreatic lipase in order to be effective and to be included in the micelles. Therefore, the sitosterol ester is first hydrolyzed to sitosterol and fatty acids inside the living system. It is well established that sitosterols, structural analogues of cholesterol, have been shown to substantially reduce total and LDL-cholesterol concentration. The basic mechanism of action of sitosterol is that, in appropriate conditions, they can become efficiently incorporated into the micelles in the intestinal lumen, displace the cholesterol, and lead to its precipitation with other, non-solubilized sitosterols. Cholesterol absorption, both from the diet and from the enterohepatic circulation, is strongly reduced in the presence of sitosterols¹² and the unabsorbed cholesterol is excreted in the faeces, increasing its concentration at this level. The second hydrolytic product is omega-3 or n-3

fatty acids. They are pleiotropic molecules with a broad variety of biological actions including hypotriglyceridaemic, anti-aggregatory, anti-inflammatory and antiarrhythmic responses¹³. These fatty acids could play a key role in the management of hypertension and hyperlipidemia and in the prevention of several diseases such as coronary heart disease, type 2 diabetes and insulin resistance¹⁴. These effects are mediated by alterations in circulating plasma lipids, eicosanoids, cytokine and physicochemical properties in the phospholipid membrane. When added to the diet, both EPA and DHA can alter the membrane phospholipid composition of the cells, alter eicosanoid synthesis and regulate transcription factor activity¹³. Supplementation with omega-3 fatty acids favourably modifies serum and tissue lipid alterations; the most consistent finding is a drastic reduction in fasting and postprandial serum triglycerides and FFA¹⁵. This has been observed with EPA and DHA alone¹⁶ and with their combination in fish oil. Reduced VLDL production by the liver¹⁷ largely results from (i) decreased availability of FFA released from adipose stores, (ii) suppression of lipogenic activity, (iii) an increase in the activity of triglyceride-synthesising enzymes (DGAT and PAP), (iv) the induction of genes involved in fatty acid oxidation and (v) an increase in phospholipid synthesis¹⁸. This regulation of gene expression proceeds through the inhibition of SREBP-1 and the activation of PPAR, which omega-3 fatty acids can interact with¹⁹. Net production of apoB is also reduced²⁰. An increased lipolytic activity of lipoprotein lipase (LPL) in extrahepatic tissues completes the hypotriglyceridemic effect witnessed with omega-3 supplementation²¹.

Another important finding of our study was that sitosterol esters increased the retention of protein in the body decreasing its excretion in faeces. Therefore, it can be used as an important treatment alongwith protein rich diet to million of children suffering from protein energy malnutrition (PEM) of which commonest forms is kwashiorkor, marasmus and marasmic-kwashiorkor.

Hypercholesterolemia is an important risk factor of Cardiovascular Disease. Therefore, in combination, sitosterols and omega-3 fatty acids offer a more comprehensive strategy for not just optimizing circulating lipid levels, but also as blood cholesterol lowering agent. In

combination sitosterol and omega-3 fatty acid produce hypocholesterolemic effect by reducing cholesterol absorption by increasing its excretion in faeces and demonstrating triglyceride and non-HDL lowering effects.

In conclusion, the present investigation demonstrated that our newly developed sitosterol esters (EPA-DHA sitosterol ester and ALA sitosterol ester) can be used for treatment of hypercholesterolemia, among which the nutraceutical effect of higher dose of EPA-DHA rich sitosterol ester was maximum.

Experimental

Materials :

A standard β -sitosterol sample was procured from Fluka Chemicals and analyzed at the laboratory by gas chromatography (GC). Fish oil (Mega-Shelcal capsules from Elder Pharmaceuticals, India) was used as the source of eicosapentanoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), and the GC analysis of the fish oil showed that the oil contained 32% EPA and 22% DHA. Refined and bleached linseed oil procured from V.K.V.K. Oil Limited, Kolkata, India, was used as the source of alpha linolenic acid (ALA), and the GC analysis of the oil showed the presence of 54% ALNA in the oil.

Thermomyces lanuginosus lipase (Lipozyme TLIM), used as biocatalyst, was a generous gift from Novozyme India, Ltd., Bangalore, India. The original moisture content of the enzyme (2%, w/w) was kept intact to initiate the reaction. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from SRL, Mumbai, India.

Preparation of sitosterol ester by packed bed bioreactor :

Sitosterol ester was prepared in packed bed bioreactor by biocatalyst technology⁹.

Animals :

The feeding experiment was performed according to the norms given by Animal Ethical Committee, Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta. Male Wistar rats weighing between 150–200 g, after 1 week of adaptation, were assigned to 6 groups as shown in Table 1. Those in group 1 were fed with normal stock diet with groundnut oil as the source of fat. The other

groups were fed with 1% cholesterol in addition to the stock diet. Sitosterol esters were force fed to four groups as a nutraceutical at different dosages. The rats were housed in cages under a 12-hour-light/12-hour-dark. The rats were anaesthetized at the end of four weeks, and 5 ml of blood was drawn from each animal.

Analysis of plasma lipids :

Blood samples for laboratory analyses were taken into EDTA-containing vacuum tubes after 12 h fasting. Plasma was separated by centrifugation and stored at -70°C until analyzed. In the analysis of lipid profile plasma lipids, samples were taken into glass centrifuge tubes and homogenized with different proportions of chloroform/methanol (vol/vol) and then centrifuged. Redistilled water was added to the mixture and the chloroform layer was separated in a separatory funnel. The chloroform was then evaporated to obtain the plasma lipids. According to the standard methods, the lipid components such as total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol and triglyceride were analyzed using enzyme kits supplied by Merck.

Analysis of faecal lipids and proteins :

The samples of freeze dried diet and faecal matter were extracted. The total crude lipid content of faecal matter were measured with the help of Soxhlet apparatus. The total crude protein content was measured by the method of Kjeldahl¹⁰.

Quantitative isolation and analysis of faecal steroids :

In the experiment, stools collected into clean dry weighed utensil were stored at 4°C . The moisture content of the faecal matter was analysed. The faecal lipid obtained was saponified with 20 ml of *N* NaOH in 90% ethanol and the contents of the bottles were refluxed for 1 h. The unsaponified portion of the lipid was given for GC analysis¹¹ and the amount of excretion of cholesterol and phytosterol was calculated.

Statistical analysis :

All results were expressed as the mean value \pm S.E.M. Statistical significance of the difference among values was analyzed by one-way ANOVA. Results were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

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